

Case Report

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A Rare Case Report of Desmoplastic Small Round Cell Tumour, Over the Mons Pubis: Diagnosis and Management

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ABSTRACT

This case report describes our difficulty in arriving at a Clinical diagnosis and management of a rare malignancy. Our patient is a 28-year old female, P3 +2, whose last child birth was 3 months ago. She presented with a complaint of a swelling over the mons pubis of 2 years duration. The swelling was painless and she had genital mutilation as a child. There was no swelling on any other part of her body. On clinical examination, there was a large mass over the mons pubis, it measured 9.8 x 8.0 x 6cm. It was firm, non-tender, with smooth walls and well-defined margins and there was no bruit. There were no palpable lymphadenopathy and She had a type II Female Genital Mutilation (FGM). She was evaluated and asked to series of investigation including CT scan of the pelvic and she subsequently had excision of the mass which was sent for histology and immunohistochemistry. The result showed Desmoplastic small round cell tumour. Our patient unfortunately was lost to follow-up. However, our experience with this case will still come in handy in the future, especially the need to consider Desmoplastic small round cell tumour as a differential of a tumour growth over the mons pubis..

Keywords: Vulval mass, Desmoplastic tumour, Diagnosis, Management

CASE PRESENTATION

Our patient is a 28-year old female, P3 +2, whose last child birth was 3 months ago, she was yet to resume menstruation. She presented to our gynecological clinic with complaints of a swelling over the mons pubis of 2 years duration. The swelling was said to have started

gradually but was progressively increasing in size. The swelling was painless. There was no swelling on any other part of her body. There was no history of chronic cough. She had genital mutilation as a child. She had no chronic medical illness like hypertension nor diabetes mellitus. She

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had no risk factors for sexually transmitted diseases. She does not react to any drug and she was not currently taking any medications. Clinical examination revealed a young lady, who looked healthy, her weight was 53.0kg and her height was 1.52m, her Body Mass Index (BMI) was 22.94kg/m². She was not in any obvious distress. Neurologically, she was alert and well oriented to time, person and place. Her chest was clinically clear. Her pulse rate was 76 beats per minute. It was regular and full volume. Auscultation of the heart revealed first and second heart sounds, with no added sounds. Abdominal examination revealed an abdomen that was flat, it moved with respiration, it was soft, there was no area of tenderness with no organomegaly, there was no ascites and the bowel sounds were normal. There was an obvious large mass over the mons pubis, it measured 9.8 x 8.0 x 6cm. It was firm, non-tender, with smooth walls and well defined margins. The mass did not change in size or shape. When the patient was asked to perform the valsalva maneuver. There was no bruit. There were no palpable lymphadenopathy. Examination of the vulvar did not reveal ulcers. She had a type II Female Genital Mutilation (FGM). Speculum examination of the vagina and digital vagina examination did not reveal any

Figure 1: A mass over the Mons Pubis, with intraurethral Catheter

abnormality. A per rectal examination did not reveal any abnormality. The following diagnosis was made, vulvar mass? Cause to rule out lipoma and clitoridal inclusion cyst.

INVESTIGATION

Full blood count done was normal. HIV, Hepatitis B and C screening were all normal. Venereal Disease Research Laboratory (VDRL), test was non-reactive. The serum, electrolyte urea and creatinine were all normal. Pelvic ultrasound scan revealed a normal sized uterus that measured 2.7cm in AP diameter, it was anteverted. The endometrial plate was thin. Both ovaries demonstrated multiple follicles of varying sizes. The conclusion was that it was an essentially normal study.

Ultrasound scan over the mass revealed “a large complex mixed echogenic cystic mass with large lobules of hydrodensities centrally. This has dense low level echoes within it. There are also anechoic areas around it. It is thick walled with echogenic and irregular inner margin. Mild eccentric and peripheral vascularity was noted. No Calcification is seen within it. There are no complete septations within it. It is extending from the pubic bone superiorly to the vulva inferiorly. It is anterior to the pubic bones. The conclusion from the USS was tat of a complex perineal mass with central areas of necrosis or hemorrhage”.

CT scan of the pelvis revealed “a large rounded heterogeneously iso-to-hypo-dense mass lesion located antero-superior to the pubic symphysis and extending inferiorly to the perineal region, below the coccygeal level. Following contrast administration, it shows heterogenous and predominantly peripheral moderate enhancement (Hugo). There is an eccentric right sided ovoid region of non-enhancing hypo density (Hu 0 26), suggestive of an area of cystic degeneration, necrosis or long standing haemorrhage, no calcification or significantly fatty area is noted within it. It measures about 11.3 x 7.9cm in maximum sagittal dimension. There is minimal erosion of

Figure 2: Pelvic CT Scan of the patient

the anterior aspect of the underlying pubic bone, however no bony destruction or intrapelvic extension is noted at this time. The uterus, cervix and vagina are unremarkable. No discrete uterine or adnexial mass is noted. The endosigmoid intestinal segment and urinary bladder are also preserved. No significant pelvic lymphadenopathy. The rest of the pelvic bones are normal. The conclusion from the pelvic CT Scan was that of a large complex inferior pelvic and perineal soft tissue mass. The differentials were, angiomyxoma of the vulva, perineal epidermal inclusion cyst and giant acrochordon or fibroepithelial polyp. Ultrasound guided biopsy of the vulval mass was not done.

TREATMENT

She was counselled for an excisional biopsy. This was done under spinal anesthesia. There was local infiltration with xylocaine + adrenaline, to reduce bleeding. A transverse incision was made over the skin overlying the mass. This was deepened to the subcutaneous tissue the mass was separated from the subcutaneous tissue and its attachment to the pubic bone posteriorly by blunt and sharp dissection. It measured about 9.8 x 8.0 x 6cm and was round and firm in consistency. Bleeding vessels were ligated. The cavity of the mass was closed with PDS, 2/0. The redundant skin was trimmed and was closed in a subcuticular fashion using PDS 2/0. Immediate postoperative period was satisfactory. The mass was sent for histology and immunohistochemistry. She was placed on antibiotics and analgesics. She did well in the postoperative period and on the third day, she was discharged home to be seen in gynaecology clinic at 6 weeks post-operative.

Figure 3: The mass after it was excised and bisected at surgery.

Figure 5a: Photomicrographs of Haematoxyline & Eosin (H & E) Sections (X4 Magnification)

Histology Report

Histological sections show sheets of malignant mesenchymal tumour with ill-defined pseudocapsule. The tumour is arranged in nests separated by desmoplastic stroma. The tumour cells are spindle, moderately pleomorphic with ill-defined scanty eosinophilic cytoplasm and ovoid to round vesicular nuclei. Some have inconspicuous nuclei. The tumour is angiocentric also displaying geographic necrosis with vague peripheral palisading composed of malignant and inflammatory cells. Focal areas of lymphovascular invasion is present. Mitotic figures are florid (15/hpf)

Figure 5b: Photomicrographs of Haematoxyline & Eosin (H & E) Sections (X10 Magnification)

Immunohistochemical Profile:

- (1) Vimentin Moderate diffuse positivity
- (2) Desmin Focal positivity
- (3) Neuron-Specific Enolase Mild focal positivity
- (4) CD 34 Non reactive (Negative) for the tumour

Figure 6a: Photomicrographs of Immunohistochemistry Antibodies Vimentin

Figure 6b: Photomicrographs of Immunohistochemistry Antibodies Desmin

Figure 6c: Photomicrographs of Immunohistochemistry Antibodies NSE

Figure 6d: Photomicrographs of Immunohistochemistry Antibodies Cd34

The final diagnosis from the immunohistochemistry was: Desmoplastic small round cell tumour. She was counselled on the need to be admitted and to eventually be placed on chemotherapy. Since then she failed to return to the hospital for chemotherapy despite several telephone voice calls. Thus, she was eventually lost to follow up.

DISCUSSION

The original description of Desmoplastic Small Round Cell Tumour (DSRCT) was reported by Gerald & Rosai in 1989.¹ This is a rare soft tissue Sarcoma. It has been documented to arise commonly in the abdomen or pelvis in young boys and adolescents. DSRCT are found in almost all age groups.² Our patient was a 28-year-old female, P₃⁺². Young men usually in the age 20-30 years are the most affected by DSRCT. These group accounts for 85-90% of total cases.³ Our patient was a female. As of the year 2013, less than 200 cases had been reported in the world literature.⁴

In terms of gross pathology, tumours are generally large in size with uneven morphology, and after dissection the surfaces are gray. In our patient the tumor measured 9.8 x 8.0 x 6.0cm and weighed 200grams. Cut section showed a solid variegated appearance and a thickened dark tan capsule. (P.E x 6).

In terms of morphology, DSRCT's consist of poorly differentiated round cells with cytoplasmic densities and connective tissue stroma. Typically, DSRCTS show immunohistochemical positivity for desmin, cytokeratin, vimentin, and CAMS S.2.⁵ (See Figure 5).

There appear to be a paucity of literature published on DSRCT, thus making an accurate diagnosis challenging as in our case. The initial clinical diagnosis was that of a mass over the mons pubis? Cause, to rule out lipoma or a clitoridal inclusion cyst. The tissue of origin and the clinical symptoms have not yet been specified for DSRCT. Its morphological features, immunohistochemical, biomarkers & molecular properties are said to be relatively distinct.⁶ Our patient presented with a swelling over the mons pubis of 2 years duration. Our literature search did

not show any other reported case of DSRCT located over the mons pubis. Most of the previously reported cases were seen in the abdominopelvic cavities of adolescents.

⁶ However, many case reports have described this tumour originating from different organs such as the brain, testis, extremities, and salivary glands ⁷⁻¹⁰ Clinical presentation depends on the primary location of the tumour as well as the stage of the disease. Diagnosis of this tumour requires histopathological analysis of tissue taken from it, together with immunohistochemistry and molecular testing.² Our patient had an excision of the mass and the sample was subjected to both histology and immunochemistry. She also had an ultrasound scan of the tumor and pelvic CT Scan, a serum electrolyte, urea and creatinine and a full blood count, with results as earlier enumerated. The immunohistochemistry confirmed the diagnosis of a Desmoplastic small round cell tumor. Other investigations that could be done, include, a magnetic resonance imaging & ultrasound guided biopsy of the mass², but these were not done in our patient.

Our patient had an excisional biopsy of the mass over the mons pubis as shown in figure 1. The plan following the immunohistochemistry result was to investigate her and offer her chemotherapy, however despite repeated calls to her telephone number as documented in her case file, she did not show-up for this. Thus, she was lost to follow-up. There are options for treating Desmoplastic small round cell tumors, which could be surgery (which our patient had), radiotherapy and chemotherapy.²

The overall 5-year survival rate of DRSCT is said to be approximately 15%.¹¹ In most of the patients the tumor has metastasized at the time of presentation. This thus makes the median survival time to be quoted at 17 to 25 months¹².

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